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HRADAYA DIPAKA NIGHANTU : A REVIEW OF ITS THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL CONTRIBUTIONS TO AYURVEDA

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Abstract

The word Nighantu in Ayurveda denotes the group of drugs, synonyms, properties and their description of part used. Ayurveda treatment possesses herbal, mineral, animal origin products which mainly take part in the treatment of various health ailments. Hridaya Dipaka Nighantu, a 13th century lexicon contains very useful plant information. This book contains eight Vargas i.e. Chatushpada, Tripada, Dwipada, Ekapada, Dwinama, Ekanama, Nanartha and Mishraka varga. This Nighantu only mentions the synonyms of the drugs and does not include any description of the Guna-Karma (properties and actions) of the drug. Total 468 drugs are elucidated in this Nighantu. Bopadeva, author of Hridayadipaka Nighantu was an erudite scholar and a grammarian and authored 26 books on diverse subjects like astrology, medicine, literature etc. However, his medical contributions did not come to light enough. Even after the emergence of Bhavprakash Nighantu, the significance of Hridayadipaka Nighantu persisted. Bopadeva has mentioned the drugs explained in Laghu Vagbhat or Ashtang Hridaya, thereby giving the name "Hridayadipaka Nighantu" to the lexicon.

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Introduction:

Nighantu, a Sanskrit term meaning "the end of words" or "lexicon," refers to a genre of ancient Indian medical texts that have played a pivotal role in the development and evolution of Ayurveda, the traditional Indian system of medicine. These texts serve as a comprehensive repository of Ayurvedic knowledge, providing a detailed understanding of various concepts, terms, and principles that underlie the practice of Ayurvedic medicine. Nighantu texts are essentially dictionaries or glossaries that explain the meanings of technical terms, identification of drug, and elucidate the principles of Ayurvedic pharmacology.

Author of Hridayadipaka Nighantu :

During the medieval period, Bopadeva or Vopadeva was a popular person in the field of scholarship. He is well-known for writing religious books and as a grammarian. His contributions in the field of medicine did not come to the light as it should. He inherited the rich medical tradition from his father Keśava who was a Royal Physician. Vopadeva wrote a book on medicine by name Śataśloki, with his own commentary known as Candrakala. The family of Bopadeva has contributed much in the field of Nighantu literature. The father of Vopadeva, Keśava, wrote a book called Siddha Mantra that has important information about dravya. Vopadeva wrote a commentary on this work known as 'Prakāśa Candra Vyākhyā' and 'Gūdarthādīpikā on Śārangadhara Samhitā. He also wrote a separate book on Nighantu known as Hṛdayadīpakā.¹

Hṛdayadīpakā was a very popular Nighantu. Even after Bhava Prakāśa Nighantu made an appearance, the popularity persisted. The quantity of manuscripts that are on display in the several libraries spread across our nation's regions is proof of this. The Saraswathi Bhavan Library in Varanasi has six manuscripts. A manuscript of this work is also in the possession of the Post Graduate Institute of Indian Medicine Library, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi. While few are written in Bengali, the majority are in Devanagari scripts.

The author and his date

Bopadeva, also known as Vopadeva, is the author of this work. He was the son of Kesava and a disciple of Dhaneswara, as stated in the book's conclusion. He describes himself as "the son of Kesava, a vaidya (physician), and the disciple of Dhaneswara, who is revered by the wise." Bopadeva resided in Vedapura, a town on the banks of the Varada river in Maharashtra, which was the capital of King Simharaja. His teacher, Dhaneswara (or Dhanesa), was also a physician from Vedapura.

Bopadeva mentions his parents as Ārogya (mother) and Vaidyanatha (father). Vaidyanatha may be an epithet for his father, Vaidyācārya Keśava, while Ārogya is likely an epithet for his mother, Lakṣmī, as stated in the introductory verse of the commentary. This statement is supported by the introductory verse of Hṛdayadīpakā where salutation is offered to श्रीवैद्यनाथ who is also अज (unborn) and अक्षर (indistructible). अज and अक्षर are synonyms of Viṣṇu (Keśava) who is Lord of Śrī (Lakṣmī) as well as vaidyas in the incarnation of Dhanvantari.

Vopadeva was attached with Hemādri as a friend and colleague. Hemādri is a well known commentator and written commentary Ayurveda Rasayana on Astanga Hṛdaya. Hemadri was the chief minister of Mahādeva (1260-1271 A.D.) and later on of his successor Ramacandra (1271-1309 A.D.). Vopadeva is said to be Pandita to king Mahādeva, therefore the date of Vopadeva is fixed accordingly as the end of 13th Century A.D.²

Other works of Bopadeva

He has written a book Harilila on the advice of Hemādri and his biography during last stages of his life. The books Harilila and Muktapphala are said to be commented upon by Hemādri himself. Vopadeva was an erudite scholar of Ayurveda, Vyākaraṇa, Sahitya, Jyotisa and Dharmasāstra. He was a good poet and a physician. He himself has presented a list of his works in the concluding portion of his book Harilila. According to this, he wrote 10 books on Vyākaraṇa, 9 books on Ayurveda, One on Jyotisa, 3 on Sahitya and three on Bhagawata. Totally he wrote 26 books.

Text of Hridayadipaka:

चतुस्त्रिद्वयेकपादैकनामनानार्थमिश्रकैः।
वगैर्निघण्टुसंक्षिप्तैर्वक्ष्येहृदयदीपकम्।।

In essence, Bopadeva aimed to create a comprehensive and accurate reference text that would provide clear information on medicinal plant of Ashtang Hridayam, while avoiding errors and ambiguities. He achieved this through the Hridayadeepak Nighantu. In the Middle Ages, Vagbhata's 'Ashtang Hridayam' remained the primary foundation for the study and teaching of Ayurveda. Due to its concise and comprehensive nature, it gained immense popularity. The availability of over 30 commentaries on 'Ashtang Hridayam' is an indicator of this fact. For the students of Ashtang Hridayam, a Nighantu text was necessary to introduce the medicinal plant described in it. So that, the 'Hridayadeepak Nighantu' was composed.

Vopadeva himself states that he has mentioned the dravya from Swalpa Vāgbhaṭa or Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaya in the Nighantu in the following verses:

सस्वल्पवाग्भटकृति- प्रभृतिप्रकाशचक्रेनिघण्टैममलं द्विजवोपदेवः।

Because of this features this book has been named as 'Hridayadīpakā'. This Nighantu has been written on the basis of synonyms but not on the basis of gunakarma. Also there is much similarity in the description of Amarakoṣa and Hridayadīpakā.

Amarakosa	Hradayadipika
गायत्रीबालतनयःखदिरः।	गायत्रीखदिरोबालपत्रः।
चव्यंतुचविका।	चव्यंकोलंचचविका।
शतमूलोबहुसुताभीरुः।	शतपत्राबहुसुताशतमूली।
नाकुलीसुरसारास्त्रासुगन्धागन्धनाकुली	नाकुलीसुगन्धागन्धनाकुली
अभयंनलदंसेव्यममृणालंजलोद्भवम्।	उशीरमभयंसेव्यममृणालंजलाशयम्।

Hradayadipika has described many drugs by way of synonyms but not mentioned its *gunakarma*. The varieties of soma drugs are also described. The subject matter of Hradayadipika has been divided into eight vargas.

The classification is as follows:³

No	Varga	No. of drug
1.	<i>Chatuspada varga</i>	37
2.	<i>Tripada varga</i>	42
3.	<i>Dwipada varga</i>	100
4.	<i>Ekapada varga</i>	123
5.	<i>Dwinama varga</i>	36
6.	<i>Ekanama varga</i>	118
7.	<i>Nanartha varga</i>	12
8.	<i>Misraka varga</i>	-

1.ChatuspadaVarga: In this particular section each verse is dedicated to a single drug, with only synonyms in four lines. Drug mention in these *varga* like *Strotonajan, Sauvira, Takshrya, Svarna* and others mentioned in below table.

Drug name	Latine name	Drug name	Latine name
<i>Yashtimadhu</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra Linn.</i>	<i>Dhanvyavasaka</i>	<i>Alhagi pseudalhagi Desv.</i>
<i>Rodhra</i>	<i>Symplocos racemose Roxb.</i>	<i>Eranda</i>	<i>Ricinus communis L.</i>
<i>ShwetaRodhra</i>	<i>Symplocos chinesis Lour.</i>	<i>Rakta eranda</i>	<i>Jatropha curcas L.</i>
<i>Brihati</i>	<i>Solanum indicum Linn.</i>	<i>Mandukaparni</i>	<i>Centella asiatica l.</i>
<i>Kantakari</i>	<i>Solanum xanthocarpum Scrad & Wendl.</i>	<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Tinospora cordifolia Wild.</i>
<i>Pippali</i>	<i>Piper longum Linn.</i>	<i>Putikaranja</i>	<i>Holoptelea integrifolia roxb.</i>
<i>Gajkrishna</i>	<i>Piper retrofractum Vahl.</i>	<i>Kaidarya</i>	<i>Pogamia pinnata</i>
<i>Haridra</i>	<i>Curcuma longa Linn.</i>	<i>Kakandola</i>	<i>Mucuna monosperma Wight</i>
<i>Darunisha</i>	<i>Berberis aristata DC.</i>	<i>Kapikachchu</i>	<i>Mucuna pruriens linn.</i>
<i>Trivrut</i>	<i>Operculina turpethum Linn.</i>	<i>Sariva</i>	<i>Hemidesmus indicus Linn.</i>
<i>Masurvidala</i>	<i>Ipomoea petaloidea Choisy.</i>	<i>Kalanusari</i>	<i>Ichnocarpus frutescens Linn.</i>
<i>Indravaruni</i>	<i>Citrullus colocynthisLinn.</i>	<i>Shatavari</i>	<i>Asperagus racemosus Willd.</i>
<i>Vishala</i>	<i>Trichosanthes tricuspidata Lour.</i>	<i>Chandana</i>	<i>Santalum album Linn.</i>
<i>Vidarigandha</i>	<i>Desmodium gangeticum Linn.</i>	<i>Raktachandana</i>	<i>Pterocarpus santalinus Linn.</i>
<i>Pritiparni</i>	<i>Uraria picta Jacq.</i>	<i>pitachandana</i>	<i>Lingoum santalinum L.f.</i>
<i>Nakuli</i>	<i>Aristolochia indica L.</i>	<i>Manjishtha</i>	<i>Rubia cordifolia linn.</i>
<i>Yavasa</i>	<i>Fagonia Arabica L.</i>		

2.TripadaVarga : In this particular section each verse is dedicated to a single drug, with synonyms in three lines. Drug mention in these Varga below table. Other dravya like *Vanshalochana, Shilajita, yavkshara, Sarjikakshara, Gandhaka, Sarjarasa.*

<i>Aragwadha</i>	<i>Cassia fistula L.</i>	<i>Agnimantha</i>	<i>Premna serratifolia l.</i>
<i>Devdaru</i>	<i>Cedrus deodara Roxb.</i>	<i>Jayanti</i>	<i>Clerodendrum phlomidis L.f.</i>
<i>Chitraka</i>	<i>Plumbago zeylanica L.</i>	<i>Kakoli</i>	<i>Roscoea procera Wall.</i>
<i>Apamarga</i>	<i>Achyranthues aspera L.</i>	<i>Kshirakakoli</i>	<i>Lilium pilyphyllum L.</i>
<i>Karkatashrugi</i>	<i>Pistacia chinensis Bunge ssp.</i>	<i>Shatapushpa</i>	<i>Anethum graveolens L.</i>
<i>Katurohini</i>	<i>Picrorhiza kurroa Royle.</i>	<i>Chatra</i>	<i>Foeniculum vulgare Mill.</i>
<i>Amlavetasa</i>	<i>Garcinia pedunculata Roxb.</i>	<i>Raktagunja</i>	<i>Abrus precatorius L.</i>
<i>Matulunga</i>	<i>Citrus medica L.</i>	<i>Shwetagunja</i>	<i>Abrus fruticulosus</i>
<i>Nagkesara</i>	<i>Mesua ferrea L.</i>	<i>Bakuchi</i>	<i>Psoralea corylifolia L.</i>
<i>Prativisha</i>	<i>Aconitum bisma</i>	<i>Shobhanjana</i>	<i>Moringa oleifera Lam.</i>
<i>Ativisha</i>	<i>Aconitum heterophyllum Wall.</i>	<i>Raktashobhanjana</i>	<i>Moringa concanesis Nimmo.</i>
<i>Kurantaka</i>	<i>Barleria prionitis l.</i>	<i>Koshataki</i>	<i>Luffa acutangula L.</i>
<i>Bana</i>	<i>Barleria strigose Wild</i>	<i>Dhamargava</i>	<i>Luffa aegyptiaca Mill.</i>
<i>Indrayava</i>	<i>Holarrhena antidysenterica L.</i>	<i>Jatamansi</i>	<i>Nardostachys jatamansi DC.</i>
<i>Gandhamasi</i>	<i>Selinum vaginatum C.B.</i>	<i>Shwetavacha</i>	<i>Paris polyphylla Sm.</i>
<i>Vacha</i>	<i>Acorus calamus L.</i>	<i>Kamala</i>	<i>Nelumbium speciosum Willd.</i>
<i>Nilakamala</i>	<i>Nymphaea nouchali Burm.f.</i>	<i>Kumuda</i>	<i>Nymphaea alba L.</i>

<i>Raktakamala</i>	<i>Nymphaea rubra Roxb.</i>		
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3.DwipadaVarga: In this particular section each verse is dedicated to a single drug, with synonyms in two lines. Like *Triphala*, *Trikatu*, *Saindhava*, *Madhu*, *Padmakesara*, *Saurashtri*, *Nakha*, *Vyaghranakha*, *Shukti*, *Mocharasa*, *Shrivasa*, *Sita*, *Manashila*, *Gairika*, *Swarnagairika*, *Smudrafena*. Other drug mention in these varga below table.

<i>Madana</i>	<i>Xeromphis spinose Thunb.</i>	<i>Drunpushpi</i>	<i>Leucas cephalotus spreng.</i>
<i>Ela</i>	<i>Elettaria cardamomum L.</i>	<i>Bala</i>	<i>Sida cordifolia L.</i>
<i>Brihadela</i>	<i>Amomum subulatum Roxb.</i>	<i>Atibala</i>	<i>Abutilon indicum l.</i>
<i>Alabu</i>	<i>Lagenaria siceraria Standl.</i>	<i>Nagabala</i>	<i>Sida veronicaefolia lam.</i>
<i>Kutaja</i>	<i>Holarrhena antidysentrica L.</i>	<i>Priyangu</i>	<i>Callicarpa macrophylla Vahl.</i>
<i>Murva</i>	<i>Marsdenia tenacissima Roxb.</i>	<i>Kramuka</i>	<i>Areca catechu L.</i>
<i>Pushkarmula</i>	<i>Inula racemose Hook. f.</i>	<i>Bol</i>	<i>Commiphora myrrha Nees.</i>
<i>Sarshapa</i>	<i>Brassica campestris var.</i>	<i>Sugandhabala</i>	<i>Pavonia odorata Wild.</i>
<i>Snuhi</i>	<i>Euphorbia nerifolia L.</i>	<i>Kasis</i>	<i>Ranunculus sceleratus L.</i>
<i>Kushtha</i>	<i>Saussurea costus falc.</i>	<i>Ushira</i>	<i>Vetiveria ziznioides L.</i>
<i>Tagara</i>	<i>Valeriana jatamansi Jones.</i>	<i>Dhanyaka</i>	<i>Coriandrum sativum L.</i>
<i>Vidarika</i>	<i>Puraria tuberosa Dc.</i>	<i>Gambhari</i>	<i>Gmelina arborea Roxb.</i>
<i>Kshiravidarika</i>	<i>Ipomoea digitate l.</i>	<i>Shanrgeshta</i>	<i>Flacourtia indica Burtm.f.</i>
<i>Kodrava</i>	<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum L.</i>	<i>Bhunimba</i>	<i>Sweteria chirayata Roxb.</i>

<i>Mundi</i>	<i>Sphaeranthus indicus l.</i>	<i>Arjuna</i>	<i>Terminalia arjuna Roxb.</i>
<i>Kulhala</i>	<i>Sphaeranthus senegalensis DC.</i>	<i>Gokshura</i>	<i>Tribulus terrestris L.</i>
<i>Shyonaka</i>	<i>Oroxylum indicum L.</i>	<i>Shunthi</i>	<i>Zingiber officinale Rosc.</i>
<i>Pashanabheda</i>	<i>Bergenia ciliate Haw.</i>	<i>Amalaki</i>	<i>Embllica officinalis Gaertn.</i>
<i>Arjaka</i>	<i>Orthosiphon pallidus Royle.</i>	<i>Haritaki</i>	<i>Terminalia chebula retz.</i>
<i>Sindurvar</i>	<i>Vitex negundo L.</i>	<i>Kakodumbarika</i>	<i>Ficus hispida L.f.</i>
<i>Jeeraka</i>	<i>Cuminum cyminum L.</i>	<i>Laghu kankol</i>	<i>Piper cubeba L.f.</i>
<i>Krishnajaji</i>	<i>Carum carvi L.</i>	<i>Amra</i>	<i>Mangifera indica L.</i>
<i>Musta</i>	<i>Cyperus rotundus L.</i>	<i>Gugglu</i>	<i>Commiphora mukul Engl.</i>
<i>Samnga</i>	<i>Mimosa pudica L.</i>	<i>Kumkum</i>	<i>Crocus sativus L.</i>
<i>Dugdihika</i>	<i>Euphorbia thymifolia L.</i>	<i>Shleshmantaka</i>	<i>Cordia myxa Roxb.</i>
<i>Bhallataka</i>	<i>Semecarpus anacardium L.f.</i>	<i>Chakramarda</i>	<i>Senna tora Roxb.</i>
<i>Ashthisanhara</i>	<i>Vitis quadrangularis wall.</i>	<i>Kakamachi</i>	<i>Solanum americanum Mill.</i>
<i>Erimeda</i>	<i>Acacia farnesiana L.</i>	<i>Vetasa</i>	<i>Salix caprea L.</i>
<i>Khadira</i>	<i>Acasia catechu L.f.</i>	<i>Nichula</i>	<i>Salix tetrasperma Roxb.</i>
<i>Kadara</i>	<i>Acasia polyacantha Wild.</i>	<i>Nimba</i>	<i>Azadirecta indica L.</i>
<i>Kadamba</i>	<i>Anthocephalus cadamba Roxb.</i>	<i>Mahanimba</i>	<i>Melia azedarach L.</i>
<i>Kola</i>	<i>Ziziphus jujube Lam.</i>	<i>Shati</i>	<i>Hedychium acuminatum Roscoe</i>

<i>Karkandhu</i>	<i>Zizyphus nummularia burm.f.</i>	<i>Hinsra</i>	<i>Capparis spinose L.</i>
<i>Sauvira</i>	<i>Zizyphus sativa Gaertn.</i>	<i>Grudhranakhi</i>	<i>Capparis sepiaria L.</i>
<i>Vidanga</i>	<i>Embelia ribes Burm.</i>	<i>Punarnava</i>	<i>Boerhavia diffusa L.</i>
<i>Shabarkanda</i>	<i>Dioscorea bulbifera L.</i>	<i>Varshabhu</i>	<i>Trianthema portulacastrum L.</i>

4.Ekapada varga: In this particular section each verse is dedicated to a single drug, described in one lines. *Gorochana, Ayomala, Kundaru, Ikshuvalika, Kasturikamada, Tuttha, Siktha, Kanamula, Bhadrautkata, Sauvarchala, Laksha, Pushpanjana, Satala, Parada, Krishna, Makshikadhatu, shankha, Hartala, Shaluka.* Other drugs mention in these Varga below table.

<i>Swanaksheeri</i>	<i>Euphorbia thomasoniana Boiss.</i>	<i>Raktarka</i>	<i>Catropis procera Ait.</i>
<i>Hansapadi</i>	<i>Adiantum philippense L.</i>	<i>Alarka</i>	<i>Calotropis gigantean L.</i>
<i>Neelavruksha</i>	<i>Indigofera tinctoria L.</i>	<i>Nagdanti</i>	<i>Croton oblongifolius Roxb.</i>
<i>Bilvavruksha</i>	<i>Aegle marmelos L.</i>	<i>Bharhmi</i>	<i>Bacopa monieri L.</i>
<i>Rajadana</i>	<i>Manilkara hexandra Roxb.</i>	<i>Artagala</i>	<i>Forsk.</i>
<i>Katphala</i>	<i>Myrica esculenta Buch Ham.</i>	<i>Morata</i>	<i>Maerunerium oblongifolia</i>
<i>Vellantara</i>	<i>Dichrostachys cinerea L.</i>	<i>Karveera</i>	<i>Nerium indicum Mill.</i>
<i>Jingini</i>	<i>Lannea coromandelica Merr.</i>	<i>Adraka</i>	<i>Zinziber officinalis Rosc.</i>
<i>Jyotishamati</i>	<i>Celastrus paniculata Wild.</i>	<i>Kokilaksha</i>	<i>Hygrophila spinose T. Anders.</i>
<i>Rajika</i>	<i>Catha paniculata scheidw.</i>	<i>Chavika</i>	<i>Piper retrofractum Vahl.</i>
<i>Alvaluka</i>	<i>Prunus cerasus L.</i>	<i>Sushavi</i>	<i>Momordica charatia L.</i>

<i>Akhuparni</i>	<i>Merremia gangetica L.</i>	<i>Jati</i>	<i>Jasminum officinalis L.</i>
<i>Bhargi</i>	<i>Clerodendrum serratum L.</i>	<i>Madayanti</i>	<i>Lawsonia inermis L.</i>
<i>Kasamarda</i>	<i>Cassia occidentalis L.</i>	<i>Tintidika</i>	<i>Garcinia indica chois.</i>
<i>Rasna</i>	<i>Pluchea lanceolate DC.</i>	<i>Bibhitaka</i>	<i>Termanalia bellirica Roxb.</i>
<i>Maricha</i>	<i>Piper nigrum L.</i>	<i>Shirisha</i>	<i>Albizia lebbek L.</i>
<i>Ashwatha</i>	<i>Ficus religiosa L.</i>	<i>Sunishannaka</i>	<i>Marsilea minuta L.</i>
<i>Udumbar</i>	<i>Ficus racemose L.</i>	<i>Khajuri</i>	<i>Curculigo orchiodes Gaertn.</i>
<i>Harenu</i>	<i>Vitex agnus-castus L.</i>	<i>Mushali</i>	<i>Asparagus adscendens Roxb.</i>
<i>Ashwagandha</i>	<i>Withania somnifera L.</i>	<i>Tilaparni</i>	<i>Cleome viscosa L.</i>
<i>Meshashrungi</i>	<i>Gymnema sylvestre Retz.</i>	<i>Ingudi</i>	<i>Balanites aegyptiaca L.</i>
<i>Badari</i>	<i>Ziziphus oenoplia L.</i>	<i>Jatipatri</i>	<i>Myristica fragrans Houtt.</i>
<i>Agastya</i>	<i>Sesbenia grandifolia L.</i>	<i>Girikarni</i>	<i>Clitoria ternatea L.</i>
<i>Madhavi</i>	<i>Hiptage madablota Gaertn.</i>	<i>Amrataka</i>	<i>Spondias mangifera Wild.</i>
<i>Sahadeva</i>	<i>Vernonia cineria L.</i>	<i>Talishapatra</i>	<i>Abies webbiana Lindl.</i>
<i>Gijihva</i>	<i>Onosma bracteatum wall.</i>	<i>Karpur</i>	<i>Cinnamomum camphora L.</i>
<i>Draksha</i>	<i>Vitis vinifera L.</i>	<i>Punnaga</i>	<i>Calophyllum inophyllum L.</i>
<i>Agara</i>	<i>Aquilaria agallocha Roxb.</i>	<i>Prasarini</i>	<i>Paederia foetida L.</i>
<i>Tejovati</i>	<i>Zanthoxylum armatum DC.</i>	<i>Jambu</i>	<i>Syzygium cumini L.</i>
<i>Saptaparna</i>	<i>Alstonia scholaris L.</i>	<i>Nadeyi</i>	<i>Syzygium operculatum Roxb.</i>
<i>Trayanti</i>	<i>Gentian kurroo Royle</i>	<i>Vasa</i>	<i>Adhatoda vasika Nees.</i>

<i>Karvi</i>	<i>Nigella sativa L.</i>	<i>Darbha</i>	<i>Imperata cylindrical L.</i>
<i>Kadaliphala</i>	<i>Musa paradisiaca L.</i>	<i>Kusha</i>	<i>Desmostachya bipinnata L.</i>
<i>Patra</i>	<i>Cinnamomum tamala Nees.</i>	<i>Kuchandana</i>	<i>Adenantha pavonina L.</i>
<i>Patha</i>	<i>Cissampelos pareira L.</i>	<i>Pittadaru</i>	<i>Haldina cordifolia Roxb.</i>
<i>Chinch</i>	<i>Tamarindus indica L.</i>	<i>Mudgaparni</i>	<i>Vigna trilobata L.</i>
<i>Changeri</i>	<i>Oxalis corniculata L.</i>	<i>Mashaparni</i>	<i>Teramnus labialis L.f.</i>
<i>Shitivaraka</i>	<i>Celosia argentea L.</i>	<i>Danti</i>	<i>Baliospermum solanifolium Burm.</i>
<i>Saivala</i>	<i>Ceratophyllum demersum L.</i>	<i>Dravanti</i>	<i>Croton tiglium L.</i>
<i>Jivanti</i>	<i>Leptadenia reticulata Retz.</i>	<i>Yavanika</i>	<i>Apium graveolens L.</i>
<i>Tulsi</i>	<i>Ocimum sanctum L.</i>	<i>Kulaka</i>	<i>Trichosanthes dioica Roxb.</i>
<i>Ajagandha</i>	<i>Thymus serpyllum L.</i>	<i>Kumbhi</i>	<i>Careya arborea Roxb.</i>
<i>Bhrunga</i>	<i>Eclipta alba L.</i>	<i>Dhataki</i>	<i>Woodfordia fruticosa L.</i>
<i>Shuknasa</i>	<i>Corallocarpus epigaeus Benth.</i>	<i>Nandivruksha</i>	<i>Ficus retusa L.</i>
<i>Langalika</i>	<i>Gloriosa superba L.</i>	<i>Kapittha</i>	<i>Feronia elephantum Correa.</i>
<i>Trapushi</i>	<i>Cucumis sativus L.</i>	<i>Tamalaki</i>	<i>Phyllanthus urinaria L.</i>
<i>Balamulaka</i>	<i>Raphanum sativus l.</i>	<i>Kovidaraka</i>	<i>Bauhinia purpurea L.</i>
<i>Twaka</i>	<i>Cinnamomum verum J.Presl</i>	<i>Shwetamaricha</i>	<i>Moringa oleifera Lam.</i>
<i>Karpasika</i>	<i>Gossypium herbaceum L.</i>	<i>Koraka</i>	<i>Mimusops elengi L.</i>
<i>Bimbi</i>	<i>Coccinia indica W.&A.</i>	<i>Meda</i>	<i>Polygonatum verticillatum L.</i>

<i>Devadalika</i>	<i>Luffa echinata Roxb.</i>	<i>Mahameda</i>	<i>Polygonatum cirrhifolium Wall.</i>
	<i>Rushabhaka</i>	<i>Malaxis muscifera Lindl.</i>	

5. Dwinama varga :In this varga mentioned two popular or commonly used name for one plant,

Drug	Synonym	Drug	Synonym
<i>Tinish</i>	<i>Syandana</i>	<i>Lasuna</i>	<i>Rasona</i>
<i>Durva</i>	<i>Shadvala</i>	<i>Hingu</i>	<i>Ramatha</i>
<i>Asana</i>	<i>Bijaka</i>	<i>Lavana</i>	<i>Patu</i>
<i>Kusumbha</i>	<i>Latva</i>	<i>Pilu</i>	<i>Tikshnataru</i>
<i>Buka</i>	<i>Vasuka</i>	<i>Tila</i>	<i>Lakshmi</i>
<i>Nala</i>	<i>Potagala</i>	<i>Padmaka</i>	<i>Pagjnahya</i>
<i>Tinduka</i>	<i>Virala</i>	<i>Ashoka</i>	<i>Gatashoka</i>
<i>Vidalavana</i>	<i>Pakya</i>	<i>Atasi</i>	<i>Uma</i>
<i>Upodaki</i>	<i>Potaki</i>	<i>Gundra</i>	<i>Araka</i>
<i>Bhutika</i>	<i>Bhustruna</i>	<i>Shankhapushpi</i>	<i>Shankha</i>
<i>Tala</i>	<i>Tala</i>	<i>Chanda</i>	<i>Kopana</i>
<i>Katrana</i>	<i>Dhyama</i>	<i>Kampillaka</i>	<i>Ranjana</i>
<i>Turushka</i>	<i>Taila</i>	<i>Trapu</i>	<i>Vanga</i>
<i>Shakhota</i>	<i>Gojihva</i>	<i>Vata</i>	<i>Nyogrodha</i>
<i>Shallaki</i>	<i>Char</i>	<i>Rajata</i>	<i>Rupya</i>
<i>Dhatura</i>	<i>Unmata</i>	<i>Tamra</i>	<i>Shulva</i>
<i>Suranakanda</i>	<i>Kanda</i>	<i>Sisa</i>	<i>Bhujandama</i>
	<i>Kunda</i>	<i>Madhya</i>	

6. Akanama Varga: In this Varga mentioned lists a single or commonly used name of particular medicinal plant.

Shankhini	<i>Ctenolepis cerasiformis</i> Naud.	Rudhi	<i>Habenaria intermedia</i> D. Don
Jivaka	<i>Malaxis acuminata</i> D. Don	Vrudhi	<i>Habenaria edgeworthii</i> Hook.
Dadima	<i>Punica granatum</i> L.	Vrushchikali	<i>Tragia involucrata</i> L.
Shinshapa	<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i> Roxb.	Madhuka	<i>Tectona grandis</i> L. f.
Kanguka	<i>Setaria italica</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	Shaka	<i>Madhuca indica</i> J.F. Gmel.
Kachchura	-	Shala	<i>Shorea robusta</i> Gaertn. f.
Choraka	<i>Angelica glauca</i> Edgew.	Chagkarna	<i>Terminalia crenulata</i> Roth
Lakshamana	<i>Ipomoea sepiaria</i> (Roxb.) Koen	Ashwakarna	<i>Terminalia paniculata</i> Roth
Ushaka	<i>Dorema ammoniacum</i> D. Don	Bhurja	<i>Betula utilis</i> D. Don
Kukkuti	<i>Salmalia malabarica</i> Schott.	Kasha	<i>Saccharum spontaneum</i> L.
Parpata	<i>Fumaria indica</i> Hassk.	Bhrahmasoma	<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> L.
Rohisha	-	Priyala	<i>Buchanania lanzan</i> Spreng.
Vastuka	<i>Chenopodium album</i> L.	Plaksha	<i>Ficus lacar</i> Buch.-Ham.
Gunjana	<i>Allium ascalonicum</i> L.	Mantha	<i>Premna integrifolia</i> L.
Kinshuka	<i>Butea monosperma</i> L.	Kakjangha	<i>Peristrophe bicalyculata</i> (Retz.) Nees.
Tumbaru	<i>Zanthoxylum armatum</i> DC.	Palandu	<i>Allium cepa</i> L.
Vetra	<i>Calamus rotang</i> L.	Dhanvana	<i>Grewia tiliaefolia</i> Vahl
Ankola	<i>Alangium salvifolium</i> (L.)	Marubaka	<i>Origanum majorana</i> L.

	f.) Wang.		
Tilaka	Wendlandia exerta DC.	Vishamushti	Strychnos nux-vomica L.
Kataka	Strychnos potatorum L.f.	Kebuka	Costus speciosus (Koen. ex Retz.)
Kaknasa	Martynia annua L.	Shana	Crotalaria juncea L.
Yavani	Trachyspermun ammi (L.) Sprague	Shara	Saccharum munja Roxb.
Sprukka	Anisomeles malabarica (L.)	Sharpunkha	Tephrosia purpurea (L.) Pers
Ambashtha	Hibiscus cannabinus L.	Bilvaja	Eulaliopsis binata (Retz.)
Kshavaka	Centipeda minima (L.)	Damanaka	Artemisia nilagirica (Clarke) Pamp.
Varun	Crataeva nurvala Buch.	Shanapushpi	Crotalaria verrucosa L.
Paribhadra	Erythrina indica Lam.	Yuthika	Jasminum auriculatum Vahl
Lavanga	Syzygium aromaticum (L.)	Dhava	Anogeissus latifolia (Roxb. ex DC.)
Bhavya	Dillenia indica L.	Mura	-
Susha	-	Karmarda	Carissa congesta Wight
Karabha	-	Patur	Caesalpinia sappan L.
Hapusha	Juniperus communis L.	Khajur	Phoenix sylvestris (L.)
Tanduliyā	Amaranthus spinosus L.	Kaseru	Scirpus grossus L. f.
Faninja	Ocimum basilicum L.	Matsyakshaka	Alternanthera sessilis (L.)
Soma	Ephedra gerardiana Wall.	Akshota	Juglans regia L.
Chanchu	Corchorus fascicularis Lam.	Kaoshamba	Schleichera oleosa Lour.

Panasa	<i>Artocarpus integrifolia</i> L. f.	Sthaoneya	<i>Taxus baccata</i> L.
Nalika	<i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> Blume	Mohanvalli	-
Kalashaka	<i>Corchorus capsularis</i> L.	Parusha	<i>Grewia asiatica</i> L.
Karira	<i>Capparis decidua</i> Edgew.	Shrungata	<i>Trapa natans</i> L.
Vrukshadani	<i>Dendrophthoe falcata</i> L. f.	Vishanika	-
Bahirshika	<i>Adiantum caudatum</i> L.	Ajalomi	-
Kushmanda	<i>Benincasa hispida</i> (Thunb.)	Golomi	-
Arishthaka	<i>Sapindus mukorossi</i> Gaertn.	Rama	-
Hara	-	Kulattha	<i>Dolichos biflorus</i> L.
Bastantri	-	Shefali	<i>Nyctanthes arbor-tristis</i> L.
Kanchata	<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	Pichuka	-
Ashmantaka	<i>Ficus rumphii</i> Blume	Avaru	<i>Cucumis utilissimus</i> Roxb.
Karkoti	<i>Momordica dioica</i> Roxb.	Chirbhita	-
Uttamarini	<i>Pergularia extensa</i> N.E. Br.	Nrutyakundaka	<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i> L.
Palevata	-	Champeya	<i>Michelia champaca</i> L.
Varunaka	-	Abha	-
Mujjata	<i>Orchis latifolia</i> L.	Lamajja	<i>Cymbopogon jwarancusa</i> (Jones.)
Vishadushika	-	Hijjala	<i>Barringtonia acutangula</i> (L.)
Gavedhuka	<i>Coix lachrymal</i> L.	Vruddhadaruka	<i>Argyreia speciosa</i> Sweet
Lonika	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> L.	Muchkunda	<i>Pterospermum acerifolium</i> Willd.

Vartaki	Solanum indicum L.	Karnamota	Acacia leucophloea (Roxb.) Willd.
Saha	-	Babbula	Acacia arabica Willd.
Uchchata	-	Hilamochika	Enhydra fluctuans Lour.

7. Nanartha varga : In this *Varga* give one synonym which is used for many drugs like..

Synonyms	Drugs
<i>Koshataki</i>	<i>Kshweda, Vedha, Dhamargava, Patoli</i>
<i>Sthira</i>	<i>Guha, Mudgaparni, Mashaparni, Akhuparni</i>
<i>Palasha</i>	<i>Kinshuka, Shati</i>
<i>Phala</i>	<i>Triphala, Ratha</i>
<i>Veera</i>	<i>Vidari, Kakoli</i>
<i>Chocha</i>	<i>Twaka, Nalikera</i>
<i>Deva</i>	<i>Sahadeva, Nagabala</i>
<i>Shurpaparni</i>	<i>Mudgaparni, Mashaparni</i>
<i>Loha</i>	<i>Agaru, Aya</i>
<i>Madhu</i>	<i>Madwika, Kshudra</i>
<i>Shilaja</i>	<i>Shaileya, Adrijatu</i>
<i>Tikta</i>	<i>Karanjika, Katvi</i>
<i>Keshara</i>	<i>Abjakeshara, Ahikeshara</i>
<i>Brunda</i>	<i>Twaka, Markava</i>
<i>Amruta</i>	<i>Chinna, Haritaki</i>

9. **Mishraka varga** : In this *Varga* contains a wild range of relevant information pertaining to Ayurveda like different *kalpana*, Some *Dravya*, *Churna*, *Pancharmaprocedure*, etc..Mentioned in below table.

<i>Udaka, Dugdha, Stanya</i>
<i>Piyusha, Morana, ,Dadhikurchika, Takrakurchika</i>
<i>Kilata, Dadhimanda, Mandaka</i>
<i>Takra, Udshwita, Mathita</i>
<i>Ghrita, Sarshapa tail, Vasa, Majja</i>
<i>Suramnda, Madira, Sidhu, Pakwarasa sidhu, Shitarasa sidhu</i>
<i>Sharkara, Gauda, Mardwika, Mairaiya,</i>
<i>Shukta, Madhusukta, Kanjika</i>
<i>Sauvira, Toshodaka, Shandaki, Gomutra</i>
<i>Manda, Peya, Yavagu, Vilepi, Qdana</i>
<i>Krushara, Yusha, Rasa, Khala, Kambalika</i>
<i>Kurta, Akruta, Daklavanika</i>
<i>Raga, Khadava</i>
<i>Rasala, Vesavara</i>
<i>Laja, Dhana, Pruthuka, Ulumbika</i>
<i>Kulmasha, Samite, Udmantha, Saktu</i>
<i>Pupalika, Pupa, Pinyaka,</i>
<i>Vallura, Shulya, Katukamatsyaka</i>
<i>Vastra, Pichu, Kapala, Taruna, Valaya, Nalaka</i>

<i>Shadadharana churna</i>
<i>Navayasa churna</i>
<i>Vidalapadaka, Pratyanjana</i>
<i>Phalavarti</i>
<i>Prastara shweda, Nadi sweda, Pinda sweda</i>
<i>Prayogika dhumpana, Shodhana dhuma, Sneha dhuma</i>
<i>Ashchotana, Anuvasana, Niruha, Navana</i>
<i>Panchanga, Dashanga</i>
<i>Jivaniya gana, Mishakaodana</i>
<i>Bhutodana, Vatya, Payasa</i>
<i>Kshievruksha, Chaturamla</i>
<i>Daha, Osha, Plosa, Vidaha</i>
<i>Dava, Davathu, Dhumaka</i>
<i>Amlaka roga, Hallasa</i>
<i>Utklehsha, Trupti, Udarda roga</i>
<i>Shrama, Klama, Kavalika</i>
<i>Vikeshika, Kusha, Shikhara</i>
<i>Kikkisa, Vali, Sansarjana</i>
<i>Nishvasana, Pravahika, Avapidaka</i>
<i>Jaladra, Utkshepa, Mana</i>
<i>Panchakarma</i>

Conclusion:

The Hridaydeepak Nighantu described only different synonyms of plant not given the *Guna*, *Karma* and other information of this plant. In these Nighantu is divided into eight *Vargas*, *ChatushpadaVarga* in which all four quarters of the verse describe one plant with its synonyms. In *TripadaVarga* there are three quarters of the verse describe one plant's synonyms. *DwipadaVarga* there are two quarters of the verse describe one plant. In *EkapadaVarga* each quarter of the verse describes a different medicinal plant. *DwinamaVarga* mentioned two popular names for each medicinal plant are listed. In *EkanamaVarga* one popular name for each medicinal plant is listed. *NanarthaVarga* mentioned medicinal plant with multiple synonyms. Last the *MishraVarga* a wide range of essential information related to Ayurveda described like different *kalpana*, process of *panchakarma*, different *roga* etc. This Nighantu, although brief, is remarkably valuable plant's synonyms and other information about Ayurveda.

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